

IMPACT ON REFRACTORY LINING DUE TO THE TRANSITION FROM CARBON-BASED FUELS AND REDUCTANTS TO HYDROGEN: SEPARATING MYTHS FROM FACTS

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ABSTRACT

The global drive to significantly reduce greenhouse gas emissions is pushing industries to adopt hydrogen as both a reducing agent and fuel for high-temperature processes. While some knowledge exists on the impact of hydrogen-rich reducing atmospheres on refractory linings from established industrial processes like glass manufacturing, ammonia or syngas synthesis, and natural gas-based direct reduced iron (DRI), the use of hydrogen as a reductant for iron production is gaining traction as a key solution for the steel industry's transition to net-zero emissions. This involves using hydrogen in small percentages to replace coal in blast furnaces and, more significantly, substituting natural gas with hydrogen in the DRI process, potentially up to 100 %. Moreover, the growing demand for fossil-free fuels has spurred the development of innovative and optimized hydrogen and syngas generation technologies.

While new and established processes differ in their specific conditions, there is a limited amount of information available in the literature about the long-term effects of hydrogen-rich atmospheres on refractories. Recent studies have yielded contradictory results compared to earlier research, making it challenging to discern myths from facts and accurately assess the performance and lifespan of refractory linings in these environments. This presentation aims to share fact-based findings from ongoing research and our experience in various industries, providing insights into the impact of hydrogen on refractory linings as a function of process conditions and testing parameters.

INTRODUCTION

The iron and steel industry is responsible for roughly 8 % of global energy demand and 7 % of global CO₂ emissions. A primary strategy for reducing CO₂ emissions in steelmaking is to transition away from traditional coal-based blast furnaces and basic oxygen furnaces. Established alternatives include coal-based and natural gas-based direct reduced iron (DRI) production processes. Despite the significant CO₂ emissions associated with coal-based DRI using rotary kilns, these processes offer a potential CO₂ emission reduction of 38 % [1], [2]. The predominant DRI technology involves a gas mixture of methane (CH₄), hydrogen (H₂), and carbon monoxide (CO) in a shaft kiln process, referred to as natural gas (NG)-based DRI, which can achieve up to a 61 % reduction in CO₂ emissions. Increasing the hydrogen (H₂) content in the reducing atmosphere further enhances CO₂ savings, with emerging fully hydrogen-ready (up to 100 %) shaft kiln DRI units promising a remarkable 97 % CO₂ reduction. Consequently, there is a surge in ongoing and announced projects for natural gas and hydrogen-based DRI shaft kiln units, as summarized in Table 1.

Currently, over 70 % of global DRI production, including ongoing and announced projects, relies on shaft kiln technologies [2].

Table 1. Overview of Ongoing and Officially Announced DRI Shaft Kiln Projects in Chronological Order Excluding Planning Pipeline (Adapted from [3]).

Plant	Capacity (Mtpa)	Reducing Gas	Commissioning Year
Baosteel Zhanjiang, (China)	1.0	Mixed NG, H ₂ , coke oven gas	2024
Tosyali (Algeria)	2.5	NG to H ₂	2024/2025
H ₂ Green Steel (Sweden)	2.1	H ₂	2025
SSAB, Hybrit	1.3	H ₂	2025
ArcelorMittal Spain (Asturias)	2.5	NG to H ₂	2025
Liberty Steel, Australia (Whyalla)	1.8	Mixed NG and H ₂	2025
OMK (Russia)	2.5	NG	2025
Salzgitter AG (Germany)	2.0	Mixed NG and H ₂	2026
Thyssenkrupp (Germany)	2.5	NG to H ₂	2026
ArcelorMittal Dofosco (Canada)	2.5	NG to H ₂	2026
Vulcan Green Steel (Omam)	2.5	NG to H ₂	2026
ArcelorMittal France (Dunkirk)	2.5	H ₂ and NG	2027
Blastr Green Steel (Finland)	2.0	H ₂ and NG	2026 - 2030
Liberty Steel (Romania)	2.5	NG to H ₂	2027 - 2030
ArcelorMittal Belgium (Ghent)	2.5	NG to H ₂	Until 2030
Tata Steel (Netherlands)	---	---	Until 2030
ArcelorMittal (Germany)	Approx. 2.0	NG to H ₂	2030
Liberty Steel Group Dunkirk (France)	2.0	Mixed NG and H ₂	---

Figure 1. Tube Furnace with Controlled Heating Zones. (Left) Schematic drawing of the tube furnace and sample position within the furnace. (Right) Exemplary test specimens.

Wear Mechanisms in DRI Shaft Furnaces

From a refractory perspective, several wear mechanisms are prevalent in both established and emerging DRI shaft kiln technologies, including:

- **Abrasion:** The mechanical wear caused by the movement of iron ore pellets/fines within the furnace.
- **Thermomechanical load:** Stress and strain from temperature changes and material movement.
- **Chemical wear:** Reaction of refractory lining materials with hydrogen/carbon monoxide/water vapor.

The primary change in refractory wear mechanisms is driven by the anticipated use of elevated hydrogen levels, which can impact abrasion and thermomechanical load. The following sections will focus on refractory testing in the context of these emerging hydrogen-based DRI shaft kiln processes.

Holistic Considerations for Controlled Hydrogen Testing

To accurately assess refractory performance in hydrogen-rich environments, meticulous control of all relevant parameters is essential, mirroring the rigorous approach taken in direct reduction processes. These parameters impact the interaction with the iron ore and the refractory itself:

- **Temperature:** The temperature at which the process is conducted is a critical factor in the rate of chemical reactions and the degradation of refractory materials.
- **Pressure:** The pressure within the furnace can influence the rate of chemical reactions and the flow of gases.
- **Duration:** The length of exposure to the hydrogen-rich atmosphere is a key factor in determining the extent of refractory degradation.
- **Reducing Gas Composition:** The composition of the reducing gas, including the concentration of hydrogen, can have a significant impact on the rate and type of reactions that occur.

When evaluating a refractory sample, it is important to consider its:

- **Dimensions:** The size and shape of the sample can affect its interaction with the reducing gas.
- **Chemical Composition:** The chemical makeup of the refractory material will influence its susceptibility to chemical attack by hydrogen.
- **Mineralogical Composition:** The types of minerals present in the refractory will determine its resistance to degradation.
- **Density:** The density of the refractory impacts its resistance to abrasion, thermal shock, and overall mechanical stability.
- **Porosity and Pore Structure:** The volume and distribution of interconnected pores in the refractory affect its permeability, and the rate of chemical reactions, influencing its overall durability under reducing conditions.
- **Permeability:** The ability of the refractory to allow gases to pass through its pore structure, which can affect how it responds to chemical reactions.
- **Usability:** The ease with which the sample can be tested and

its suitability for measuring performance changes before and after exposure to reducing atmospheres.

Other important refractory properties for DRI applications include abrasion resistance, mechanical strength, high-temperature performance (hot properties), and thermal shock resistance.

How to Measure Refractory Performance

While weight loss measurements are often used to assess refractory degradation, it is essential to understand the origin of the weight loss and how it relates to changes in the performance of the refractory lining:

- **Mass, Density, and Porosity:** These fundamental properties influence the material's structural integrity.
- **Permeability and Microstructure:** These factors affect the flow of gases and the material's vulnerability to chemical attack.
- **Chemistry and Mineralogy:** These determine the refractory's resistance to specific chemical reactions, such as reduction by hydrogen.
- **Mechanical Performance:** This includes the material's resistance to thermal shock, its strength, and its ability to withstand abrasion.

EXPERIMENTAL

The results presented in this paper are drawn from two sources:

- **FIELD:** Data from a large-scale DRI shaft kiln processing approximately 1 million tons of iron ore per , utilizing a mixed atmosphere of natural gas (NG), carbon monoxide (CO), carbon dioxide (CO₂), water vapor (H₂O), and hydrogen (H₂) with in-situ reforming. Due to confidentiality, detailed results from this field study will not be presented.
- **LABORATORY:** Data obtained from controlled experiments conducted in a tube furnace, as illustrated in Figure 1. The laboratory experiments employed test specimens measuring 150 mm × 25 mm × 25 mm. Polished sections were prepared from the front and back of the samples for examination using scanning electron microscopy (SEM).

Figure 2. Batch Furnace.

The laboratory tests were conducted using an electrically heated Nabertherm RHTH 120/600/18 H₂-CO tube furnace at the Technology Center Leoben (TCL). The test specimens were exposed to either 100 % hydrogen atmosphere or a diluted hydrogen atmosphere containing a low amount of residual nitrogen. The hydrogen flow rate was set to 100 L/h. An alternative experimental setup, depicted in Figure 2, involved stacking the samples with spacers in between and placing them in an electrically heated "box" type furnace – the hydrogen flow rate was set at 200 L/h.

RESULTS and DISCUSSION (Due to the limited space available for this presentation, only a selection of results will be discussed)

Influence of Test Parameters on Reduction Rate

To investigate the influence of different test parameters on the reaction of refractories with hydrogen, a lightweight alumina-silica brick, designated as grade L280, was exposed to hydrogen. The chemical composition of the L280 brick is 61 % alumina (Al_2O_3), 35 % silica (SiO_2), with trace amounts of phosphorus pentoxide (P_2O_5) < 0.1 % and iron oxide (Fe_2O_3) < 1 %.

The reduction of most refractory oxides by hydrogen, such as silica, results in volatile products. However, it's important to note that not all reduction products are gases. Consequently, weight loss measurements are commonly used to assess the rate of reduction, although they may not fully account for all reaction products. However, the reduction of silica (SiO_2), a major component of refractories, is a relatively slow process at temperatures relevant for DRI applications, making it challenging to obtain significant results in short-term tests lasting hours or even weeks [4]. It is crucial to remember that refractory linings are designed to withstand years of use in industrial applications.

Considering the high open porosity and permeability of the lightweight alumina-silica L280 brick, it is reasonable to assume that the reduction of iron oxide and silica within the refractory is facilitated under hydrogen exposure [4],[6]. Significant changes in the refractory due to reduction can be expected under these conditions.

The L280 bricks were subjected to both 100% hydrogen atmospheres and diluted hydrogen atmospheres, with variations in gas flow rate, exposure duration, and temperature. These conditions are outlined in Table 2. Two distinct furnace setups were employed for the testing: a tube furnace with direct heating and a batch furnace with indirect heating. The tube furnace facilitated a comparison of different sample positions, allowing us to account for potential downstream effects (Figure 4). All tests were conducted at atmospheric pressure. Table 2 presents the test conditions and corresponding weight losses.

Table 2. Measured Weight Losses of a High Alumina Lightweight Brick.

Set-up	H ₂ Atm.	Duration (h)	Temperature (°C)	Wt. loss %
100 L/h	100 %	200	1200	1.5 (av.)
100 L/h	100 %	200	1200	1.4 (av.)
100 L/h	100 %	100	1200	0.6 (av.)
100 L/h	Diluted with N ₂	200	1200	0.6 (av.)
100 L/h	Diluted with N ₂	200	1200	0.8 [Zone1]
100 L/h	Diluted with N ₂	200	1200	0.3 [Zone1]
100 L/h	Diluted with N ₂	200	1200	0.1 [Zone1]
200 L/h	100 %	200	1000	< 0.1 (av.)
200 L/h	100 %	200	1200	11.2 (av.)
200 L/h	100 %	200	1200	13.5 [P1]
200 L/h	100 %	200	1200	8.9 [P2]
200 L/h	100 %	200	1400	21.1 (av.)

Notably, samples exposed to higher flow rates in the batch furnace exhibited a 7-fold increase in weight loss compared to samples in the tube furnace. This finding aligns with the established principle that

the rate of reduction increases with the H₂ flow rate when mass transport controls the reaction kinetics [7]. While the flow rates in both furnaces were relatively low, diffusion control is likely the dominant factor.

Regarding the influence of dilution, samples exposed to 100 % H₂ for 200 hours showed a greater weight loss than those exposed for only 100 hours or those exposed to a diluted H₂ stream containing 40 % N₂. This strong effect of dilution on the reduction rate is consistent with existing literature. For instance, Crowley et al. [8] observed a significantly higher weight loss in bricks exposed to 100% H₂ compared to those exposed to mixtures containing 75 % H₂ – 25 % N₂ or 50 % H₂ – 50 % N₂.

The observed weight losses can be attributed to microstructural changes within the refractory. SEM analysis (Figure 3) revealed the presence of alumina (1), metal droplets (2), mullite (3), and a glassy phase (4).

Figure 3. SEM-BSE Image of a L280 Grade Alumina-Silica Brick After Exposure to 100 % H₂ for 200 Hours at 1200 °C.

The reduction of unstable components within the refractory led to the formation of reduced iron and phosphorus-containing metallic droplets (observed in phosphate-bonded samples). This was accompanied by the reduction of SiO_2 to volatile $SiO(g)$. Both reactions contributed to the observed weight loss. Analyzing the individual weight losses of the samples exposed to 100 % hydrogen in the batch furnace (Figure 2 and Table 2) revealed a consistent trend: samples placed in the inner positions (P1) consistently exhibited higher weight losses than samples placed at position 2 (P2) within the same test run. No correlation was observed between weight loss and distance from the gas inlet in this instance. This suggests a significant influence of direct heating and uneven heat distribution, as the proximity of these samples to the heating elements at the furnace walls points towards a direct impact. This finding aligns with the well-established principle that silica reduction is highly temperature-dependent, exhibiting a steep non-linear increase in reaction rate above approximately 1000 °C. It is further crucial to consider downstream effects – changes in gas speed, flow velocity, and composition – arising from the interaction of the reducing gas with the samples. Tube furnaces with low gas velocities are ideal for well-controlled case studies due to their simple geometry and predictable flow dynamics.

Figure 4. Alumina-Silica Sample Positioning in the Different Zones of the Tube Furnace. This figure illustrates the placement of six alumina-silica samples within the tube furnace. The values depicted represent the percentual weight losses for six samples positioned from upstream to downstream (left to right).

In our experiments, the Reynolds number (Re) for the hydrogen flow in the tube was 220, indicating a laminar flow regime, which is typical for $Re < 2300$ [9].

According to fluid dynamics [9] for laminar flow within a tube, the fluid velocity follows a parabolic profile, with the fluid at the center of the tube moving at the highest velocity. The fluid velocity is zero at the walls of the tube due to friction. Consequently, samples positioned near the center of the tube, as in our setup, experience the maximum gas velocity. If more samples are placed in sequence within the tube, as in Figure 2, the first samples exposed to hydrogen in Zone 1 would react, producing volatile species, including water vapor. Samples in Zone 2 would then be subjected to a mixture of hydrogen and these volatile reaction products. Samples in Zone 3 would eventually be exposed to an even more diluted hydrogen atmosphere.

As previously discussed, the dilution of hydrogen generally slows down the reduction rate. Water vapor, in particular, enhances the stability of SiO_2 against hydrogen reduction from a thermodynamic perspective [4].

These observations, combined with recent research findings [10], prompted us to conduct trials placing samples in all three zones of the tube furnace. The results (Table 3) confirmed a trend of decreasing reaction rate for the samples as they were positioned further downstream in the furnace.

Table 3. Physical Properties of L280 Grade Alumina-Silica Samples (a) Intact, (b) After 200 Hours at 1200 °C Under Oxidizing Conditions, and (c) Reducing (100 % H_2) Atmosphere.

Property	(a) Intact	(b) Oxidizing	(c) 100 % H_2
Bulk Density (g/cm^3)	0.88	0.93	0.93
Initial US E-modulus (GPa)	2.72	2.72	3.8
Final US E-modulus (GPa)	not applicable	2.8	3.5
Delta US E-modulus (%)	not applicable	+ 3	- 8
CMOR (MPa)	1.7	1.7	1.6
Delta Mass (%)	not applicable	0	- 1.5

Physical properties of the refractory samples were measured both before exposure to hydrogen (intact sample) and after exposure to 100% hydrogen at 1200 °C for 200 hours. For comparison, physical properties were also measured after exposing the samples to

oxidizing conditions (1200 °C for 200 hours). Independent of the atmosphere, densification occurred during temperature treatment, as evidenced by the changes in bulk density (Table 3). Ultrasonic (US) E-modulus values, an indicator of material strength, generally improved after temperature treatment under oxidizing conditions. This is likely due to densification, which increases the material's density and strength. This effect was more pronounced for samples exposed to up to 60 % hydrogen (+7 % - not shown in Table 3) but it was diminished under 100 % hydrogen conditions due to the increased weight loss. In line with this observation, 8% decrease in US E-modulus was measured after hydrogen exposure. Measurements of cold modulus of rupture indicated an impact of hydrogen reduction on the refractory mechanical properties, too. However, the changes are hardly significant, and more data are needed for confirmation. The observed reduction of silica upon hydrogen exposure as confirmed by weight loss and mineralogical investigations could also negatively affect abrasion resistance, a main wear mechanism in DRI installations.

CONCLUSIONS

This selection of experimental trials highlights the importance of carefully choosing the right testing conditions to accurately assess the impact of hydrogen on refractory linings. Our findings demonstrate that silica reduction within the refractory increases with:

- Increasing temperature
- Increasing gas flow
- Increasing hydrogen concentrations
- Increased exposure time

While these findings were anticipated, our research also demonstrates the significant impact of the experimental setup and sample positioning on these critical parameters. Weight loss was attributed to changes in the microstructure of the refractory, which ultimately led to a slight decrease in its mechanical properties.

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